
APPLYING THE THEORY OF PLANNED BEHAVIOR AMONG STUDENTS AT PREPARATORY LEVEL TO EXPLORE THE DETERMINANTS OF STUDENTS' INTENTION, IS THERE A DIFFERENCE?

Dr. Sulaiman Abdullah Saif Alnasser Mohammed

Department of Self-Development, College of Preparatory Deanship
University of Ha'il, Saudi Arabia

Dr. Attallah Alqatan

Department of Self-Development, College of Preparatory Deanship
University of Ha'il, Saudi Arabia

Dr. Firas Alqaadan

Department of Self-Development, College of Preparatory Deanship
University of Ha'il, Saudi Arabia

Dr. Fadi Gauanmeh

Department of Self-Development, College of Preparatory Deanship
University of Ha'il, Saudi Arabia

ABSTRACT

Attitudes, subject norms, perceived control, are the determinants of student's intension, inspired by the theory of planned behavior (TPB) and the literature review, we found that examining the theory on universities students at preparatory-level is limited particularly on the Saudi Arabia context, the students at preparatory-level are considered in a level between the high school and college level, the objective of this study is to explore the intention of those students towards starting their own business. The authors were inspired from the study of (W. J. Aloulou, 2015). This study was conducted on 363 students in Saudi at University of Ha'il. Structured questionnaires were randomly distributed among students of preparatory-level in University of Hai'l, Saudi. Partial least square technical analysis is utilized to examine the proposed relationships. The result of study showed that attitudes and perceived control are significantly related to student's intension. However, we have found no relationship between subject norms and intension which contradict majority of previous studies. Furthermore, there are differences in response between male and female students. Worth mentioning, Majority of previous studies overlooked the importance of

preparatory-level student's intention towards entrepreneurship. The striking feature of this study is an in-depth emphasis on exploring application of theory of planned behavior on preparatory level context. Moreover, to the best of authors' knowledge, this is a pioneer study that comprehensively examines the linkage of components of TPB with student entrepreneurial intension among preparatory-level students in Saudi.

Keywords: Theory of planned behavior (TPB), Entrepreneurship, Saudi Arabia

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1. INTRODUCTION

The creation of a successful entrepreneurs has been a priority in many countries, the countries' gross domestic production has been progressing due to the tax generated from small and medium enterprises. Therefore, Entrepreneurs represent some important assets to many governments around the world. However, the debate remained unsolved on the reasons behind the person willingness to become an entrepreneur, the reasons remained debatable due to the differences between legal origin, culture of the people and easiness of establishing business from one place to another. The growth in world gross domestic production are expected to hit 1.5% due to the Coronavirus, according to the press release by economic forum, the normal expectation was approximately between 2.5%-2.9%. The slowdown of economic growth once associated with number of new graduates seeking to find their way in the job market makes it urgent to study the reasons behind the intentions of the students to start their own business. Indeed, once we know the reasons we could draw more attentions towards easiness of policies. Therefore, studying student's intention plays an important role in determining growth of small and medium enterprises in the country. In the kingdom of Saudi Arabia, the government represented in the establishing of vison 20-30 have made it a priority to include the improving of small and medium enterprises as one of vision 20-30 goals, high-level concern is given to business entrepreneurs, the policy tends to increase students who set their path towards generating new enterprises. Well, we found that few studies have tried to examine student's intentions towards entrepreneurship practically in Hail, at Hail university, in preparatory level. The total number of students at preparatory level in university of Hail estimated to reach 5194 students in 2019, 2103 students are males where 3614 are females, they are distributed among three streams of studies, 2506 in science stream, 2199 in humanities stream and 1012 in medical stream. The purpose is to enhance their ability in fundamentals of Math, English and Business. Well, entrepreneurship course is offered to students in humanities stream and science streams, the course covers the basic details on becoming an entrepreneur. Meanwhile, it covers topics such as business plans, SWOT analysis and Innovation in business. In this paper, we are trying to understand the reasons behind Saudi student's intentions to start their own business, the application of theory of planned behavior in the preparatory year context is found to be limited particularly in Saudi universities. The first chapter have showed an introduction addressing the main objective, second chapter will browse into the theoretical framework and literature, third chapter is concerned about the result of the study where last chapter will discuss the result in details relating it to the literature.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

Entrepreneur education is examined extensively in the literature, it seeks to provide students with the necessary knowledge, skills and motivation to enough success in doing business. Indeed, browsing into the literature provided us with enlightening points about entrepreneur education. Firstly, the importance of entrepreneur education in enhancing the self-employment which result in minimizing the side effects of unemployment rate on the economy particularly in the time of recessions. Secondly, we have found a debate in the literature on the validity of the argument that entrepreneurship education is encouraging students to start their own business, the finding of research is inconsistent, the reasons could be attributed to the difficulties encountered while evaluating the entrepreneurship education (Bergmann, Hundt, & Sternberg, 2016; Nabi, Holden, & Walmsley, 2010; Vesper & Gartner, 1997), it is very complicating to affirm that studying entrepreneurship courses helps students in starting their own business (Sivarajah & Achchuthan, 2013). Secondly, theoretical background played an important role in shaping the studies, TPB the theory of planned behavior by (Ajzen, 1985, 1991b) has explained the association between intentions and individual behavior (Krueger, Jr. & Brazeal, 2018; Krueger & Brazeal, 1994), the theory is linking also intentions with decisions to become entrepreneur. Moreover, entrepreneurship scholars have viewed human capital as a determinant of entrepreneurial intentions (Davidsson & Honig, 2003; Honig & Davidsson, 2000), there is another theory base which has shown to play a role in explaining the entrepreneur education named the entrepreneurial self-efficacy (Mcgee, Peterson, Mueller, & Sequeira, 2009), this theory talks about the believe in oneself to perform the tasks, entrepreneur education will enhance the ability of an individual to perform business task. Thirdly, in Saudi Arabia context the studies are few (Ali, 2016; W. J.

Aloulou, 2016; Choukir, Aloulou, Ayadi, & Mseddi, 2019), students with relative having business tends to be more exposed to starting their own business, (Choukir et al., 2019) investigated in their papers students' entrepreneurial intentions among business students at one of the Saudi universities, they found that having parents, relatives, and friends, who are entrepreneurs significantly influences the entrepreneurial intentions. Worth noting, according to (Lorz, Mueller, & Volery, 2013) the research of entrepreneurship education and how it influences entrepreneurial intentions is still limited. Furthermore, studies above were mostly concentrating on students out of the preparatory stage or later stages of the university (W. Aloulou, 2015), they are about to graduate, and graduating students who are more concerned about getting a job than those away from graduation time (Lemmink, Schuijf, & Streukens, 2003; Francisco Liñán, Urbano, & Guerrero, 2011). Thus, this is a gap in previous research concerning entrepreneurial intentions. Well, these studies indicated the potential international use of Ajzen's model to predict entrepreneurial intent of university students, Although the TPB has successfully predicted students' entrepreneurial intentions in different contexts as presented above, its utility at predicting intentions in Arab countries has not been well established. Our attention turns to applying the TPB (Ajzen, 1991a) in Saudi context and to replicating the (Iakovleva, Kolvereid, & Stephan, 2011) study to the same context. Therefore, this study addresses the influence of studying entrepreneurship on student's intentions to start their own business, the sample is limited to Saudi students in preparatory-level at university of Hail for the year 2019-2020. This study therefore aims to contribute to the current debate by examining the effectiveness of entrepreneurship education in Saudi.

2.1. Theoretical grounding: theory of planned behavior

The samples of our studies, the students at University of Ha'il at preparatory level, the sample fits more towards the theory of planned behavior, however, there is a move towards using the human capital theory among researchers (Passaro, Quinto, & Thomas, 2018; Tan, 2014;

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Unger, Rauch, Frese, & Rosenbusch, 2011), but this theory requires information about individuals with work experience, knowledge, skills and other competences, our students are still at the starting stage, they have almost no background about entrepreneurship, they came from high schools directly. Therefore, theory of planned behavior is suitable and fit for them. The theory of planned behavior is a theory which treats human behavior as a result of factors influencing the intentions, it is from school of psychology, the theory is presented firstly as a result of extending the theory of reasoned action, (Ajzen, 1985) by his article "From intentions to actions: theory of planned behavior." Meaning that if a person evaluates the attitude as successful and others wants him convert the attitudes into subject norms, the motivation is developed which made him likely to do the motivated action. Meanwhile, in this study, we want to examine the impact of entrepreneur education on the intension of students to start their own business, the theory says intension is determined by attitude, subject norms and perceived behavioral control as it appears in Figure 1.

Source: (Ajzen, 1991b)

Figure 1 Theory of planned behavior

2.2. Attitude in Entrepreneur education, impact on Intension

The term is related to individual ability to move from the desire of being a self-employed or the desire to work for someone (Ajzen, 1991b; Souitaris, Zerbinati, & Al-Laham, 2007; Zhang, Duysters, & Cloudt, 2014). Moreover, many studies presented evidences about the impact of attitudes on intention, the intention is likely to convert into behavior, this behavior is the starting of own business, studies such as (Krueger, 2011; Raposo & do Paço, 2011; Shariff & Saud, 2009; Tkachev & Kolvereid, 1999) found that attitudes are the beliefs which is directly and positively related to entrepreneur intension, because of these findings researchers have suggested that entrepreneur education had better to consider syllabus which concentrate of changing the personal attitudes, this could enhance the person intension towards creation of business and removing the unseen barriers towards starting business. The environmental factors have seen to impact the attitudes, the person confidence level in performing the job are developed through self-efficacy, research papers such as (Edelman & Yli-Renko, 2010; Estay, Durrieu, & Akhter, 2013; Fayolle & Liñán, 2014; Heuer & Liñán, 2013; Zanakis, Renko, & Bullough, 2012) provided evidence that when a person belief that he is capable of starting the business, he could move towards achieving the project. Therefore, in the Saudi context, there is an ample room to examine the whether attitude in entrepreneur education have a relationship with intention, the above literature supported the proposing of the following hypothesis testing.

H1: The relationship between Attitude in Entrepreneur education is positively related to Intension

2.3. Subject norms in Entrepreneur education, impact on Intension

Opinions from the group surrounding the life of an individual plays an important role in motivating the intensions (Boyd & Vozikis, 1994; Hockerts, 2017; Küttim, Kallaste, Venesaar, & Kiis, 2014; Solesvik, Westhead, Matlay, & Parsyak, 2013; Thuy, Ngoc, & Hong, 2017) , social pressure will help to speed up a person intention to start a business, these pressure and opinions are referred to as subject norms (Krueger, Reilly, & Carsrud, 2000). Indeed, (Hill, Fishbein, & Ajzen, 1977) described subjective norm as “perceived social pressure to engage or not to engage in behavior.” Sometime a person social opinions and social recognition enhance the intentions to proceed with implementing the business proposal (F Liñán, 2004; Francisco Liñán, 2008; Francisco Liñán & Fayolle, 2015)The relationship between subject norms and intentions are debatable, there are studies confirming that subject norms enhance intention significantly (Iakovleva & Kolvereid, 2009; Iakovleva et al., 2011; Kolvereid, 1996; Kolvereid & Moen, 1997; Uygun & Kasimoglu, 2013). However, there are studies which found that social norm sometimes has a low impact on intention, they also considered social norms as the weaker factor among the others (Armitage & Conner, 2001; Autio, Keeley, Klofsten, & Ulfstedt, 1997; Conner & Armitage, 1998; Francisco Liñán & Chen, 2006). Therefore, in the Saudi context, there is an ample room to examine whether subject norms in entrepreneur education have a relationship with intention, the above literature support the proposing of the following hypothesis testing.

H2: The relationship between Subject norms in Entrepreneur education is positively related to Intension

2.4. Perceived behavioral control in entrepreneur education, impact on Intension

(Bandura, 1977) extended self-efficacy theory from social cognitive theory, he added the concept of perceived behavioral control, according to Bandura an individual expectation, experience associated with a repeated failure determine the intention towards starting the business, he had categorized expectations into the self-efficacy and outcome expectancy. Bandura defined self- efficacy as the conviction that one can successfully execute the behavior required to produce the outcomes (Ajzen, 2002; Ajzen & Madden, 1986; Utami, 2017; Walinga, 2008). Moreover, outcome expectancy refers to a person's estimation that a given behavior will lead to certain outcomes. Therefore, in the Saudi context, there is an ample room to examine the whether subject norms in entrepreneur education have a relationship with intention, the above literature support the proposing of the following hypothesis testing.

H3: The relationship between Perceived behavioral control in entrepreneur education is positively related to Intension

3. METHODOLOGY

3.1. Data

The study is limited to students in preparatory –level at University of Ha’il in Saudi Arabia, the reason for this limitation because the objective of this paper is to know to what extent the determinants of intention play a role in student’s willingness to start their own business, this will be performed through hypothesis testing. The total sample population is the total number of students at preparatory level in university of Hail in 2019-2020 which is estimated to reach 5194 students in 2020, 2103 students are males where 3614 are females, they are distributed among three streams of studies, 2506 in science stream, 2199 in humanities stream and 1012 in medical stream. The method of questioning is a survey adopted from (Francisco Liñán & Chen, 2006), This questionnaire is utilized previously on different context Such as Spain and

Taiwan. The questionnaire consists of questions on each construct, the student is answering based on 5 Likert scales (1 = Strongly disagree and 5 = Strongly agree) and nominal scales. The survey is distributed via an online method, the student will enter into a survey form build-in web site, the students at preparatory-level is the targeted sample, this paper is written during the Covid-19 pandemic, therefore, we avoided totally handing a hard copy of the survey to the students.

3.2. Variables and Measurements

The questionnaire structure consists of questions covering the determinants of student's intention, attitudes, subject norms and perceived behavioral control. Indeed, 5 points Likert scale is used to measure the level of answers, the source of selecting measurements are as below,

- **Attitudes measurements'** items are derived from (Francisco Liñán & Chen, 2006) , the number of questions for this independent variable are 5, they are concerned about understanding whether students are attractive towards being an entrepreneur.
- **Subject norms' items** are derived from (Francisco Liñán & Chen, 2009), the number of questions for this independent variable are 3, they are concerned about the surrounding individuals and their opinions about oneself ability to become an entrepreneur , we have covered the family, friends and colleges.
- **Perceived behavioral control's items** are derived from (Francisco Liñán & Chen, 2009), the number of questions for this independent variable are 5, they are concerned about the student self confidence in his ability to start a new business.
- **Students Intension related items** are derived from (Francisco Liñán & Chen, 2009), the number of questions for this dependent variable are 6, they are concerned about the students goals in the future and its relationship to starting a new business.
- **Demographic variables**, they are family background, stream, gender and the completion of enrepnuership course. The family background and completion of entrepreneurship course are direct question, gender is measured using a dummy variable where stream is a selection between science and humanity.

3.3. Techniques used to analyze the data

In order to analyze the data, we have imported the data from excel file to Smartpls software, the using of this software takes into account the loading of factors, relationships between variables, path coefficient and the goodness of fit, the interpretations using the software is considered a great contribution in the fields of entrepreneurship intention. Indeed, PLS-SEM version 3.9 is used to analyze the data (Christian M. Ringle, Wende, & Becker, 2015), according to (Hair, J. F., Hult, G.

T. M., Ringle, C. M., & Sarstedt, 2013) partial least square could replace the normal regression analyses to more accurate multiple regression, it allows the users to run mediation and moderation without the need to separate the analysis process, smartpls is suitable when low number of samples is acquired.

4. RESULTS

In this section, a through description of data, inferential analysis and interpretation of results are implemented, following the theory of planned behavior, we have placed student intention

as a dependent variable where attitudes, subject norms and perceived control as independent variables, the theoretical frame works could be seen in Figure 2

Figure 2 the proposed conceptual framework

4.1. Demographics characteristics of respondents

Most of the respondents lives in Hail city, they have recently graduated from high schools, their ages ranges from 18- 20, male respondents accounted for almost 51 percent where the female respondents accounted for the remains 49 percent, 35 percent of the total respondents confirmed that one of his/her parents owns a business where the remain students said the opposite, 20 percent of the total students have not studied entrepreneurship where the remaining 80 percent confirmed finishing the entrepreneurship course offered at the preparatory level. In addition, 7 percent of the students came from the medial stream in preparatory level where 51 percent were from humanitarian stream, 41 percent were from engineering stream, total number of respondents were 363 students. This sample size is considered fair if we exclude the batch of 2018 students, they are students who could not complete some courses, they are given another chance to repeated the subjects.

4.2. Assessment of measurement model

In this section, we are required to measure the goodness of fit by confirming the content validity and construct validity, meaning to validate the variables and the questions asked to reflects the variables.

4.2.1. Content validity

In order to confirm the validity of the content, we are required to explore the factor loading (C. M. Ringle, Wende, & Becker, 2014) , each question asked to validate the construct should have a factor loading with minimum of ≥ 70 percent, as presented in *Table 1.0* below, none of the factors have showed less than 70 percent loading, this confirms the content validity.

4.2.2. Convergent validity

According to the SEM literature, the convergent validity refers to the extent to which a set of indicators converges in measuring the concept of concern (Christian M. Ringle et al., 2015). The convergent validity, therefore, can be confirmed using the item's reliability, internal consistency (Cronbach's a coefficient), composite reliability and the average variance extracted (AVE). According to the CFA results reported in *Table 1.0*, the factor loadings for all items were significant and exceeded the suggested cutoff level of 0.60 (Chin, Gopal, & Salisbury, 1997). In addition, the results of internal reliability using Cronbach's a values ranged from 0.70 to 0.83, higher than 0.70 as recommended by (Nunnally & Bernstein, 1994). Composite reliability values of all latent constructs ranged from 0.73 to 0.89 which were well above the acceptable level of 0.70 (Hair, J. F., Hult, G. T. M., Ringle, C. M., & Sarstedt, 2013). Similarly, the average variances extracted, reflecting the overall amount of shared

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variance among the indicators measuring a particular latent construct ranged from 0.53 to 0.74, surpassing the acceptable threshold level of 0.50 (Hair, J. F., Hult, G. T. M., Ringle, C. M., & Sarstedt, 2013). Based on the significant importance of items in measuring their own constructs, all the latent constructs having composite reliability of at least 0.70 and AVE of at least 0.50, it can be concluded that the measurement model has an adequate convergent validity level.

4.2.3. Discriminant validity

The discriminant validity is defined as the extent to which a set of variables of a particular construct differ from other constructs in the model. This implies that the variance shared among a set of items measuring a construct and their own construct is higher than the variance shared with other constructs in the model (Compeau, Higgins, & Huff, 1999)

Following the criterion suggested by (Fornell & Larcker, 1981), the discriminant validity is determined by comparing the square root of the AVE values with the correlations among the constructs. The results, as presented in *Table 1*, indicated that the square root of AVE as represented in the diagonal are higher than other values in its rows and columns. These results verifying that the model has adequate discriminant validity. In summary, the measurement model has confirmed adequate reliability, convergent validity and discriminant validity see Figure 2

Figure 3 Theoretical framework based on measurement model

Table 1 result of measurement model: Convergent Validity

Attitudes	Question No	Loading	AV	CR
	20	0.80	0.62	0.892
	21	0.82		
	22	0.72		
	23	0.80		
	24	0.78		
Subject Norms			0.74	0.898
	31	0.81		
	32	0.87		
	33	0.89		
Perceived Control			0.53	0.87
	25	0.71		

	26	0.72		
	27	0.76		
	28	0.75		
	29	0.74		
	30	0.70		
	Question No	Loading	AV	CR
Intention			0.73	0.736
	34	0.80		
	35	0.85		
	36	0.87		
	37	0.85		
	38	0.87		
	39	0.88		

4.3. Assessment of structural model

In this section, we tested the hypothesis by running the structural model, *Figure 2.0* above shows the connections between variables and the fit numbers of the structural model. However, there are five different tests to assess the structural models, path coefficient exploring the hypothesis testing, coefficient of determinations, effect size test, predictive relevance and goodness of fit. Firstly, path coefficient to explore the hypothesis testing we have implemented the bootstrapping analysis, we have found that p value of attitudes and perceived control were less than 5 percent with positive signs, this is a clear evidence that there is a positive significant relationship between attitudes, perceived control with student intention, this result supports the proposed hypothesizes. However, the relationship between subject norms and student intention showed no relationship, this is an indication that our proposed hypothesis is rejected *Table 2.0*, we may relate that to the uniqueness of the preparatory level context, these students are still young, their confidence level is higher than what we expected. Secondly, the exploring of coefficient of determinations which measures the ability of independent variables to explains the dependent variable, the *R* square of the dependent variable showed 0.637 which is considered large according to (Hair, J. F., Hult, G. T. M., Ringle,

C. M., & Sarstedt, 2013). Thirdly, effect size test is used to explore the size of influence each independent variable has towards the dependent variable, the result showed that attitudes, subject norms and perceived control showed 0.276 medium effect size ,0.002 no effect size and 0.213 medium effect size respectively, see (Cohen, 1988). Fourthly, predictive relevance explores the ability of each independent variable to predict the dependent variable *Q* square, the result showed 0.464 percent which is higher than zero, this result showed that this model is acceptable. Lastly, the goodness of fit test which explores the overall performance of the model whether measurement or structural, the result of our analysis showed that Goodness of fit as 0.45 which large enough to consider that our model is totally fit in partial least square (Hair, J. F., Hult, G. T. M., Ringle, C. M., & Sarstedt, 2013).

Table 2 Path coefficient of the research hypothesis

Hypothesis	Relationship	Stand Beta	Stand error	T-value	P value	Decision
<i>H1</i>	Attitudes->intention	0.462	0.061	7.553	0.000	Supported*
<i>H2</i>	Perceived control->intention	0.338	0.051	7.617	0.000	Supported*
<i>H3</i>	Subject norms ->intention	0.031	0.044	0.705	0.481	Not supported*

*Significance level 5 percent

5. DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

This paper attempted to apply the theory of planned behavior on the context of Saudi students in preparatory level at university of Hail, which is one of the striking feature of this study, the previous studies were lacking concentration on the said context, another feature of this study is the implementation of smartpls in analyzing the relationships. The study found that attitudes, perceived control have a direct impact on students intention, it is in line with the finding of previous studies (Ali, 2016; Francisco Liñán & Chen, 2006; Nabi et al., 2010; Utami, 2017). In addition, subject norms showed no relationship with students' intention towards entrepreneurship, it is in line with few studies which showed low influence of subject norms (Armitage & Conner, 2001; Autio et al., 1997; Conner & Armitage, 1998; Francisco Liñán & Chen, 2006), the reason could be attributed to the uniqueness of preparatory level students context, the students at this age shows more confidence towards adventures (Alias & Hafir, 2009; Antonio, 2004; Eşkisü, 2014; Hosein & Harle, 2018). Therefore, the study could enhance the interpretation pertaining to the programs of attitudes improvement and self-confidence managements, that could later change the willingness of students towards establishing their own business. Further studies could extend this work by questioning the subject norms result in this study, they may examine a possibility of a mediating or moderating variables standing in between subject norms and intention. This study has few limitations, the students responding to the study are from the Hail province, future researchers could expand the sampling to other universities in Saudi, another limitation could be the excluding of entrepreneurship education influence among preparatory level students as many of them have completed their entrepreneurship course, we believe that students with entrepreneurship knowledge are different from those with no knowledge. The study is very important to researchers and policy makers in Saudi, this study could act as a reference guide to education authority in Kingdom of Saudi Arabia as to include entrepreneurship through different streams.

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